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INTERETHNIC RELATIONSHIPS AS REFLECTED IN PLACE NAMES OF SOUTHERN TRANSYLVANIA¹

Abstract

Transylvania has a long history of interethnic contacts – both peaceful and conflicting. As a result, a multitude of either “shared” or divergent place names were recorded in all regions of the respective province throughout centuries. The focus of this article is on central-southern Transylvanian village names, most of them recorded in the Sibiu County (*județul Sibiu*), an area inhabited by Romanians, Transylvanian Saxons and Hungarians. Cases of parallel evolution, bilingualism, diglossia, folk etymology and imposition of official names (in Medieval Latin, German, Hungarian and Romanian) will be highlighted and discussed in detail below.

Keywords: Transylvania, history, place names, interethnic relationships, linguistic analyses

1. A brief introduction

Transylvania is a perfect example of an area with most visible effects of contacts among ethnic groups that have been *coterritorial*² for centuries. Most relevant among those effects are visible in the shapes and shifts of Transylvanian place names, many of which had the chance to remain in use up until the present. However, for all their importance, such names have been rather seldom approached from the perspectives of areal linguistics and contact linguistics.

I must confess there also is a personal reason why I decided to write this article. Namely, as a bilingual speaker (Transylvanian Saxon-and-Romanian) I was attracted to the double, or even multiple names of many villages of central-southern Transylvania. Many of the villages the names of which I will analyze below are located along *Valea Hârtibaciului* (*Harbachtal*). It is the area that also includes my mother’s native village, which is known to Romanians as *Vărd* and to Transylvanian Saxons (*Sächsen*) as *Werd*. From members of my mother’s family, I learned the Transylvanian Saxon (TS)³ subdialect – or *Ortsmundart* – known as *Werdërësch*;⁴ and I can also converse in the more “urban” subdialect of the nearby town of Agnita (*Agnetheln* in German – *Ugnoitëln* in *Werdërësch*).

Among other things, this article aims to highlight the richness and scientific importance of *Dicționar istoric al localităților din Transilvania* by Coriolan Suciu.⁵ The latter – a Romanian Greek-Catholic priest, with a PhD in history – managed to collect a huge amount of information regarding attestations of names borne not only by the still extant villages and cities of Transylvania, but also by

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¹ The present article contains illustrative material included in the handout (signed Andrea Bargan) which the present author delivered at the International Conference #Romania 100 – Looking Forward through the Past, Bucharest, June 25-30, 2018.

² In my use of the term *coterritorial*, I follow Shevelov (1964: 160), who – in referring to the earliest Slavo-Romanian contacts north of the Danube – makes the following observations: “A large part of the population in these areas must have been bilingual for a long period of time. This was a typical case of coterritorial languages, not just contiguous.”

³ Here is a list of the abbreviations used in this article: G = (Modern) German; H = Hungarian; L = Latin; MHG = Middle High German; ML = Medieval Latin; OHG = Old High German; R = Romanian; TS = Transylvanian Saxon.

⁴ Significant details on the village of Werd and its TS subdialect are given in Anneliese Poruciuc’s volume *Die Werder Sachsen und ihre Mundart* (2000).

⁵ A brief presentation of Suciu’s life and activity is provided by https://ro.wikipedia.org/wiki/Coriolan_Suciu. I will mention a rather sorrowful detail: Suciu passed away in 1967, while the first volume of his dictionary was in press.

many that vanished in the meantime. Suciu's knowledge of Romanian and Latin, as well as of Hungarian and German, was of much help in his presentation of all those multilingual place names, which he extracted either directly from medieval documents, or from works of his predecessors (such as Bielz, Csánki, Drăganu, Görffy, Iordan, Iorga, Kniezsa, Mazere, Scheiner, Togan, Veress and many others). What I can add to Suciu's historically oriented bird's-eye view is a series of observations on a number of central-southern Transylvanian place names from the standpoints of contact linguistics, lexicology and etymology.

2. Attestation, ethnic attribution, official imposition and folk etymology as main issues

The 12th-13th centuries represent the period during which Hungarian kings would invite German colonists to settle in Transylvania. The blanket ethnonym that eventually came to designate – in ML documents – all early German colonists in Transylvania was *Saxones* (G *Sachsen*, TS *Sächsen*, R *sași*, H *szászok*). However, the German “guests” (*hospites*) mentioned in earliest Hungarian documents were presented as *Theutonici* or *Flandrenses*.⁶ This accounts for the fact that, linguistically, TS subdialects (which actually differ from one village to another) show features that are closer to Franconian German (especially Luxembourgish) and to Flemish than to High German. In that respect, it is also worth mentioning that, in approaching specific features of the medieval German *Ostkolonisation*, historians have established that TS villages observed the Flemish type of land allotment (*flämische Hufe*), as mentioned by Nägler (1979: 47).⁷

Names of various Transylvanian place names began to be recorded in documents written in Medieval Latin, which was the language used by authorities of the Hungarian kingdom, and which, later, was also used by literate Transylvanian Saxons before they changed their denomination, from Catholic to Protestant (Lutheran). After that denominational shift, High German began to be written by TS clergymen (who also wrote local annals and chronicles); and High German was also officially used when – beginning with the final years of the 17th century – Transylvania came to be ruled by Austria. Subsequently, Transylvanian documents were written in both German and Hungarian, as long as the Austro-Hungarian Empire survived, up until the end of the First World War.⁸

In the historical context sketched above, the Romanians and their own language had a rather unusual position. First of all, although the Romanians remained as the only speakers of a Neo-Latin language in Southeast Europe (Transylvania included), they wrote no documents in either Latin or their own Romance language before the 16th century; and, when they began to write in their own language, the Romanians used the Slavonic alphabet⁹, not the Latin one.¹⁰ However, names of Romanian villages occurred (with alien spellings) in very early documents written by Hungarian and/or Transylvanian Saxon clerks and clergymen; and there also were cases in which such Romanian names were “translated” into Latin, Hungarian, or German (see below). Examples of the last category concretely indicate the bilingualism of certain clerks and scribes; also, signs of not only bilingualism, but also of diglossia (that is, usage of two different varieties of one and the same language) can be detected in the shapes of attested Transylvanian place names. For instance, early attestations as well as oral forms still used in today's TS subdialects (such as the ones I know) indicate differences between the dialectal forms shown by TS place names recorded in early medieval times and the High German forms imposed later by socio-political factors. Dialectal features may also be detected in the rather strange

⁶ See discussion in Nägler 1979: 181.

⁷ It was also Nägler (1979: 83-84) who took into consideration proofs of the participation not only of German speakers but also of French speakers (Walloons) in the first wave of West European *hospites* in Transylvania. For instance, participation of Walloons from the province of *Brabant* is indicated by the village name that survived in Romanian as *Bărăbanț* (Alba), with attestations such as *villa Baarbanth* (1299), *villa Barbantina* (1302), *Borbantina* (1339), *Borbánd* (1733), *Barabancz* (1850), *Bărăbanț* (1854) – cf. Suciu 1967: 64.

⁸ Basic information on the history of Transylvania is to be found in Pop/ Bolovan 2013.

⁹ Throughout the Middle Ages, the Orthodox Romanians of Transylvania – for their own historical reasons – chose to use Old Church Slavonic, not Greek or Latin, as their liturgical language.

¹⁰ I will not neglect to mention that, from a socio-political standpoint, the Orthodox Romanians (in contrast with Hungarians, Szeklers and Transylvanian Saxons) were considered to be a “tolerated nation” in Transylvania, up until modern times (cf. Pop/ Bolovan 2013: 89). The first significant signs of Romanian emancipation became manifest after the establishment of a Greek-Catholic denomination at the end of the 17th century.

spellings used by non-Romanian clerks who recorded Romanian names. Another aspect worthy of consideration is represented by replacements of (obscure or seemingly offensive) old Transylvanian names by “transparent” Romanian ones either immediately after Transylvania became part of the Kingdom of Romania (1918), or by more recent official decrees (such as the ones of 1964).¹¹

In regard to the relationship between documentary records and historical precedence, we may consider that the ethnic identity of the earliest settlers of many southern Transylvanian villages is indicated by the earliest attestations of the names of those villages. As visible in some of the illustrative examples below, authorities of various times duly added clear ethnic indicators to certain village names. Special cases are the names that were (and some still are) opaque, as regards origins, or, rather, as regards whether they can be referred to any common words of one or another of the languages spoken in Transylvania. Very “colorful” cases are the ones created by folk etymology, the mechanism of which is known as conflation (R *contaminare*); most distortions of that kind were caused by misleading similarity between words of two different languages.

Aspects such as the above-mentioned ones are reflected, in minute details, by the illustrative examples I analyze below. Taking into account that Suciu’s dictionary represents a historical approach, I will insist on linguistic-etymological features.¹² Since I have already explained my particular interest in a certain Transylvanian region, I will pay special attention to geographic names of the Hârtibaci basin (such as *Agnita* and *Vârd*); however, for the sake of meaningful comparison, I will also refer to names borne by villages of other areas.

3. Examples and discussions

Since I have already mentioned the town of Agnita (Sibiu),¹³ I will analyze its name here as representative of a category that has its roots in the several-century long period during which the *Saxones* were still Catholic and therefore they still believed in saints. As a result, a whole series of Transylvanian villages and cities recall patron saints of TS churches. Thus it is not surprising that R *Agnita* was first attested, in Medieval Latin, as *Vallis Sancte Agnetis* (1317), then as *Vallis Agnetis* (1329), *Scenthagata* (1349) and eventually *Szent Ágotha*, *Agnetheln*, *Agnita* (1854) – cf. Suciu 1967: 26. An example even more relevant than *Agnita* is the village name *Sînmiclăuș*, now *Sânmiclăuș* (Alba), for which the main attestations given by Suciu (1968: 130) are the following: *villa Sancti Nicolai* (1309), *Zenthmiklos* (1390), *Szent Miklos* (1733), *Bethlen-Szent-Miklos*, *Klosdorf*, *Sîn-Miclăuș* (1854). Actually, Suciu’s list attestations is longer, and three of its chronologically presented variants, namely *Olahzenmiklos* (1461), *Zaz Zenthmyklos* (1491) and *Olah Zenthmyklos* (1493), indicate that – at least during the 15th century – both Romanians and Saxons lived in the respective village, as indicated by what we may regard as ethnic markers.¹⁴ In regard to the “saintly” component of

¹¹ Suciu also took into account onomastic replacements imposed by Romanian official decrees enacted in 1964 (published in *Colecție de legi, decrete, hotărâri și dispoziții*, București: Editura Științifică, 1965). With very few modifications, the forms of the officially Romanianized place names of Transylvania appear as such in the toponymic dictionary Ghinea/ Ghinea 2000.

¹² Like Suciu’s dictionary, Năgler’s book (1979) on the colonization of Transylvanian Saxons is historically oriented; and when Năgler makes use of place names in his argumentation he resorts almost exclusively to Modern High German variants. In regard to Jordan’s comprehensive (and influential) *Toponimia românească*, published in 1963, we may only regret that the Romanian scholar could not benefit from the material of Suciu’s dictionary, which was issued four years later. More curious is the fact that there is no reference to Suciu’s dictionary in Năgler’s volume of 1979, although the latter contains a whole chapter on TS place names (*Ortsnamen*). As for the onomastic material of Ilyés’s book on “ethnic continuity in the Carpathian-Danubian Area” (1988), there is obvious bias in the respective author’s omissions of the Romanian versions of Transylvanian geographic names.

¹³ By such parentheses I indicate the Romanian counties (*județe*) to which the discussed villages belong at present.

¹⁴ From among such markers, the earliest I could detect in Suciu’s dictionary is the one manifest in the first attestation of a village now known as *Pianu de Sus* (Hunedoara), which was recorded as *Blechis pen* in 1488 (subsequently as *Oláh Pián*, in a Hungarian document of 1733). It is obvious that *Blechis* reflects TS *blëisch* (an adjective derived from TS *Bleoch* ‘Walachian’). I must add that whole pages of Suciu’s dictionary are covered with Transylvanian village names that display supplementary markers such as *Oláh-*, *Magyar-*, *Szász-*, *Román-*, or *Walach-*, most of which represent official additions.

Sânmiclăuș, the respective component remained visible in Hungarian and Romanian variants, but – most probably as a result of the Protestant renunciation of saints – it is absent from the German variant *G Klosdorf*. In fact, that variant is German proper only in its second component, *-dorf* (cf. *G Dorf* ‘village’), whereas the first component, *Klos-*, reflects a TS pronunciation of *G Klaus* (as abbreviation of *Niklaus*). I will add that another Transylvanian village name, currently used (and officialized) as *R Cloașterf* (Mureș), actually reflects the distorted way in which Romanians pronounced the whole of the compound¹⁵ that represents the TS variant of the village name for which Suciú (1967: 157) gives attestations such as ML *Praedium Nicolai* (1267), H *Zentmiklosteleke* (1356), H *Miklóstelke*, *G Klosdorf* and R *Micloșă* (1854).

Another significant category is represented by village names that show prolonged continuity in one or another language of the ones spoken in Transylvania. To begin with, according to Suciú’s presentation (1967: 166), *Cornachel* (Sibiu) stands for the earliest attestation (1306) of a village on the Hârtibaci; in the eighteenth century, under Austrian rule, the village was recorded as *Kornicsel* (1733) and *Korneczel* (1750), and in today’s Romanian spelling it appears as *Cornățel* (as included in Ghinea/Ghinea 2000). The Romanian name poses no etymological problems, since it is obviously based on R *cornățel* (which is given in an entry of MDA-I as designation of three different spiky plants); the noun under discussion clearly derived from R *corn* (< L *cornu* ‘horn’). However, I must also mention that, as early as 1319, the same village was recorded under a rather difficult parallel name – *Hortobagh*.¹⁶ Whereas what looks like a second component of that name could be referred to *G Bach* ‘brook’, a component like *horto-* (also visible in the later Hungarian name of the same village, *Hortobágyfalva*) remains obscure.¹⁷ In later times, the same village was recorded, in turn, as *Haremszdorff* (1494), *Harwasdorf* (1509), and eventually *Haarbach* (1808) – which is actually a river name – and *Harbachsdorf* (1839). The last two forms may be considered to be transparent on German ground, if we take into account that Berger’s dictionary (1993) includes an entry on the German geographic name *Haar*, which is referred to a Middle Low German *hare* (‘ridge, hill’), a word Berger considers to be of obscure origin. What I may add is that Dutch *haar* ‘stony ground’ (given in de Vries’s dictionary of 1963) provides a better explanation for the TS river name once recorded as *Haarbach*. For a semantically oriented comparison, I will add that Berger’s dictionary also contains an entry on *G Steinach*, which transparently refers to a river with a stony bed.

From a diachronic-linguistic standpoint, an approach to *Vărd/ Werd* poses by far fewer problems than the ones mentioned in the case of *Cornățel/ Haarbach*. In his entry dedicated to *Vărd*, Suciú (1968: 241) first gives the modern-age trilingual variants of the name that designates the respective village: R *Vărd*, H *Vérd*, *G Werd* (to which I may add TS *Wëirt*, which reflects the “genuine” pronunciation of the TS natives).¹⁸ The German origin of the name under discussion is doubtless, if we take into account that Berger’s dictionary (1993: 274) gives *-werth* as a kind of

¹⁵ What I mean by “whole” is that, in the case of *Cloașterf* (= *G Klosdorf*), the Romanians approximated the TS pronunciation not only of the first element (*Klos-*), but also of the second one (*-dorf*). From what I know about TS villages of my area of interest, the *-dorf* element – which occurs in German-looking compounds of the *Klosdorf* type – is actually pronounced by TS speakers as *-drëf* or *-trëf* (depending on the preceding sound in the respective compounds). Based on village names known to me, I will observe that, for instance, what Suciú gives as *Hendorf* and *Jakobsdorf* – as attestations of today’s *Brădeni* (Sibiu) and *Iacobeni* (Sibiu), respectively – should be imagined as *Hendrëf* and *Jakobstrëf*, in accordance with TS pronunciation.

¹⁶ I do not exclude the possibility that the place under discussion had been given – before the coming of the *Saxones* – by the Turkic intruders known as Pechenegs (ML *Bessi*, R *pecenegi*, H *bessenók*), who lived for a time side by side with Romanians (ML *Blaci* – that is, *Walachians*) in southern Transylvania. The two coterritorial populations were mentioned in the fundamental charter of 1224 (issued at the court of King Andreas II of Hungary) in which the freedoms of the “Teutonic guests” were mentioned (cf. Pop/ Bolovan 2013: 53-54). Another possibility is that the etymologically difficult *Hortobagh* (1319) reflects a name given by the Szeklers (H *székelyek*, R *secui*), whose presence in the area under discussion, around 1100, is indicated by both historical documents and archaeological finds (cf. Năgler 1979: 115).

¹⁷ Iordan (1963: 87) – in following Kisch (1929) – gives *Hirtibav* as Romanian counterpart of H *Hortobágy* and presents the latter as based on “Old German *Hartobach*,” considered as originally meaning something like “brook in the woods” (to which Iordan attaches a question mark).

¹⁸ As a piece of TS humor, the following punning remark would commonly be addressed to inhabitants of the village under discussion: TS *Të best vun Wëirt* = *G Du bist von Wert*, interpretable as either ‘You are from Werd’ or ‘You are of worth’.

toponymic suffix, recorded in German geographic names such as *Kaiserswerth*, *Grafenwerth* and *Nonnewerth*. Berger refers the component *-werth* to OHG *warid* (MHG *wert*) ‘island’, with Germanic cognates such as Old English *waro* ‘bank’ and Dutch *waard* ‘plot of low land protected by embankments’. This last meaning perfectly clarifies TS *Werd* as designation of a village located in the water meadow of a frequently flooding brook (the one known as TS *Ēuldbēuch*, G *Altbach* and R *Albac*). All these data sustain the idea that the village under discussion was founded by medieval Saxones. The earliest attestation, in a ML document dating from 1311, refers to the church of the village, *ecclesia de Wert*. Subsequent attestations include the following: *Werdt* (1488), *Werd* (1494), *Vert* (1532), *Verd* (1601), *Werd* (1733), *Vérd* (1760) and *Werd* (1854). It is evident that – throughout more than seven centuries – a succession of officialdoms (Hungarian, Austrian, Austro-Hungarian and Romanian) preserved, in several variants, the original TS name of the village, which is now officially known as *Vărd* (its inhabitants being called *verzeni* by local Romanians). What I will add is that over the last three decades the local TS community has diminished to a minimum (mainly due to migration to Germany); but at least, the old *ecclesia* is still standing, and the old *Sächsēsch* graveyard is in place.

Prolonged continuity is also implied, for another example, by the evolution of *Mândra* (*Mindra* in Suciú 1967: 402), as name of two southern Transylvanian villages. The one of the Sibiu County was first recorded rather late, as *Mondra* (1750) and *Mundra* (1854); a variant of the village name under discussion, given by Suciú (1967: 403), practically represents a translation of *Mândra* (< R *mândru* ‘good-looking, proud’)¹⁹ as H *Szeptelek* (< H *szep* ‘beautiful’ + *telek* ‘place’). It is also Suciú who gives, on the same page, attestations of another *Mândra* (Braşov), recorded as *Mondra* (1400), *Mundra* (1520) *Mandra* (1637) *Mindra* (1750), *Mindra* (1854). A simple explanation for the seemingly strange alternation *o/u/a/i* – in the series of non-Romanian transcriptions of one and the same name – is that non-Romanian scribes were at a loss when they had to render the peculiar Romanian vowel /i/ (earlier /ə/), which, depending on position, is written as either *î* or *â* in today’s standard Romanian.

Interlingual alterations – including some that reflect folk etymology – can be detected in the chronologically listed attestations given by Suciú (1967: 170) in the case of *Coveş*, as present-day Romanian name of a village now included in the township of Agnita. The Hungarian origin of that name is evident in most of its attestations, with some notable exceptions. Thus, whereas *Kuesd* (1357), *villa Kwes* (1403), *Kövesd* (1733) and *Köves* (1750) indicate derivation from the adjective which, in today’s Hungarian, appears as *köves* ‘stony’ (from *kő* ‘stone’), other attestations in Suciú’s list display strange deviations, as in the following cases: *Kuybesch* (1523), *Kewbesch* (1549) and eventually *Kabisch* (1850), as officialized in nineteenth-century German. What I know from TS speakers of Agnita is that the last variant transparently reflects TS *Kabēsch* ‘cow dung’ and thus appears to be an ironic-derogatory reference to the village of Coveş and its inhabitants.

Less offensive folk etymological deviations are manifest in Transylvanian village names discussed by Adrian Poruciú (1994: 100-101). His first example is the village name *Moşna* (Sibiu), recorded as *Musyna* in 1280, and as *Moschin* in 1503 (cf. Suciú 1967: 409). The Romanian origin of that name is sustained not only by the existence of a village called *Moşna* in another corner of Romania (Iaşi County), but also by the most probable derivation of the respective village name from the Romanian word *moş* (regional *muş*), meaning ‘old man, ancestor, first heir of a plot of land’ (cf. MDA-III, s.v. *moş*, with derivatives such as *moşinar* and *moşinaş*, both meaning ‘free peasant’).²⁰ Nevertheless, in German-written documents of early modern times *Moşna* appeared under a new name, *Meschen*, as if based on TS *Meschen* ‘sparrows’.²¹ In the same part of his article Adrian Poruciú gives another relevant example of folk-etymological shift, in the case of *Vurpăr* (Alba). Today’s Romanian variant of that village name (which also has its own entry in Suciú 1968: 259) appears to be just an approximation of TS *Burprich*, which was first recorded in 1248, as *Burgberg* (a spelling that looks surprisingly Modern German!), then as *Burperg* (1317) and *Borpergh* (1411), all these being easily

¹⁹ R *mândru* is generally considered to be a very early borrowing from Old Slavic (cf. Ciorănescu 2001, s.v. *mîndru*).

²⁰ Ciorănescu 2001 (s.v. *moş*) – although inclined to imagine a Latin origin for R *moş* – does not fail to mention that “in general it is considered to be an autochthonous word [...], identical with Albanian *moshë* ‘age’” (my translation from Romanian).

²¹ In presenting TS *Meschen*, as village name, Nägler (1979: 175) gives an interpretation (*Deutung*) through a Slavic term meaning ‘fly, gnat’ (*Fliege, Mücke*); he does not mention R *Moşna* though.

interpretable as German compounds (*Burg* ‘fortress’ + *Berg* ‘mountain, hill’). However, a Hungarian reinterpretation (in form and sense) was already visible in the fifteenth-century variant *Borberek* (1421), which was then recorded as such in 1760 and in 1854. Whereas R *Vurpăr* (first recorded as *Vurper* in 1733) reflects just a distortion of the TS village name, the variant *Borberek* appears to be a folk etymological compound based on H *bor* ‘wine’ + *berek* ‘slope, bank’.

As regards two other present-day villages in the neighborhood of Agnita, namely Dealu Frumos and Merghindeal, the evolutions of their names were marked by several alterations, of which some may be considered to be folk etymological. The onomastic history of what is now represented by TS *Schienëbarch* and R *Dealu Frumos* (literally ‘Beautiful Hill’) may be regarded as erratic. According to Suciú (1967: 193), in the earliest ML documentary record (1329) the name of that village appeared as *Pulcromons* (clearly based on L *pulcher* ‘beautiful’ + L *mons* ‘mountain, hill’). There followed – in 1488 and 1508, respectively – two rather divergent variants, namely *Sonnenbergh* (‘Hill of the Sun’?) and *Sommerbergh* (‘Summer Hill’?); subsequently, TS pronunciation was suggested by *Schynbergh* (1532), but not also by *Solumberg* (1733). Two other variants of the same toponym were recorded in 1854, namely the transparent G *Schönberg* and the not so transparent R *Şulemberg*. In the same list of attestations, Suciú also includes two variants of a parallel name by which Hungarians referred to the village under discussion: *Lesszes* (1762) and *Leses* (1854).²²

The final component of present-day R *Merghindeal* also seems to have something to do with R *deal* ‘hill’. However, in his entry on that village name, Suciú (1967: 391) gives three German variants, namely *Mergeln*, *Mergenthal*, *Marienthal*. For an etymology of the first, one might be tempted to propound a geological explanation, based on G *Mergel* ‘marl, diorite sand’; as for the second variant, it contains a component *-thal* (cf. G *Tal* ‘valley’) that looks like an antonym of R *-deal*; and it is only the third German variant that clearly reflects the earliest documentary reference to that village, namely ML *Vallis Marie* (1332), subsequently recorded (in what looks like a Classical Latin form) as *Vallis Mariae* ‘Mary’s Valley’. Quite possibly, as in several other cases mentioned above, the original reference was to a patron saint. In regard to the possible significance of components such as *Marien-* and *Mergen-*, I may mention that Berger (1993: 184), in his entry on the German geographic name *Mergentheim* (Baden-Württemberg), makes reference to today’s *Sankt Märgen* (originally designating a monastery in the Black Forest area); the earliest record in that case was *cella Sancte Marie in Nigra silva* (1275), subsequently recorded as *Sante Merien* (1310). These are all arguments that can be of use in an explanation of Transylvanian *Merghindeal*/*Mergenthal* (as based on an originally TS name), but they cannot really account for the shifts the respective name underwent in both Hungarian and Romanian. For instance, I could hardly apply the same explanation to H *Morgonda* (first recorded in 1506, then in 1854), since I was not able to establish any clear connection between that variant and Hungarian common vocabulary. Finally, as regards certain attestations that appear to be renderings of the Romanian variant, namely *Mergindealu* (1434), *Mergindyal* (1750) and *Mergindeal* (1854), they look misleadingly transparent, since they seem to suggest that local Romanians interpreted the TS name of the village as having something to do with the Romanian phrase *Mergi în deal* (literally, ‘Go uphill’).

Just as in the case of R *Vurpăr* (< *Burprich* – see above), reference to a hill is also visible, however dimly, in R *Chirpăr* (cf. Suciú 1967: 143).²³ Whereas the Romanian variant of that name was recorded in the 19th century, under the contracted forms *Kirper* (1850) and *Chirper* (1854), much earlier records announced present-day TS *Kirprich*: after *Kyrchperch* (1332), there came *Kyrprig* (1488), *Kyrprich* (1508) and *Kyrprych* (1532); adaptations to High German are visible in *Kirchperg* (1733) and *Kirchberg* (1854).²⁴ Compounds of the *Kirchberg* type (< G *Kirche* ‘church’ + G *Berg* ‘mountain, hill’) are also to be found among German geographic names, such as the following ones given in Berger 1993: *Kirchheim*, *Kirchzarten*, *Leutkirch*. In regard to another village name that

²² Regarding that Hungarian name of the village under discussion, I suppose it originally referred to some scouting picket, since it appears to have derived from H *les* ‘to lie in ambush, to watch’, if we also take into consideration a compound like H *leshely* ‘observation post’ (< *les* + *hely* ‘place’ – cf. Reinhart 2011, s.v. *leshely*).

²³ *Chirpăr* now stands for the center of the territorial-administrative unit (*comună*) which also includes the village of Vărd.

²⁴ It was also in 1854 when *Kürpöd*, a Hungarian variant of the village name under discussion, was recorded; etymologically, H *Kürpöd* is as opaque as above-mentioned H *Morgonda*.

represents the same type of compounds, interesting linguistic-historical conclusions may be drawn by mere reading of the chronologically arranged records mentioned by Suciu (1967: 427) in his entry on *Nocrich* (Sibiu). Today's variant of that village name, now in use among local Romanians, clearly reflects the earliest record, dating from 1263: *terra Nogrech* (< TS *nëu* 'new' + *kirich* 'church'). It appears that what once was a "new church" of the local Transylvanian Saxons was destroyed by fire (possibly during the Mongol invasion of 1241?), and, as a result, in 1349 the same village was recorded, under the new name of *Leuskyrch* (cf. TS *lëischen* = G *löschen* 'to put out a fire'). However, in the 15th century, it was the original name of the village that was translated into Latin as *Noua Ecclesia* (1402), before being mentioned again as *Lwsskirch* (1497). A return to the original name is visible in the Hungarian variant, first recorded as *Ujegyhaz* in 1674, and eventually as *Újegyház* (< H *új* 'new' + *egyház* 'church') in 1854; it was in the same year that G *Leschkirch* and R *Nocrig* were also recorded, as names of the same village.

To add a pan-Germanic – or even pan-European – perspective to my presentation of names that refer to old village churches, I will say that a compound like TS *Kirprich* actually is a perfect "synonym" of the historically famous English name *Churchill* (< *church* + *hill*). This reference to a "British connection" also provides an opportunity for me to mention the Transylvanian village known as *Viscri* in Romanian and as *Weisskirch* ('White Church') in German.²⁵ It is in Viscri (Braşov) where Prince Charles of Wales – before becoming King Charles III – purchased a piece of property, which includes a traditional Transylvanian Saxon house.²⁶

4. Conclusions

Although my list of illustrative examples is rather limited, my survey of Transylvanian village names enables me to draw some general conclusions. Among other things, it is quite obvious that entries such as the ones included in Suciu's dictionary are valuable not only for the field of historiography. They also represent a real treasure for specialists interested in diachronic linguistics, or in various effects of the coterritorial existence of ethnically different communities, or in the organizational patterns of those communities. It is worth observing that many TS village names reflect the kinds of landscapes – from water meadows to hills – that the initial settlers chose as sites for their settlements; also, many such names make reference to the (usually fortified) churches which came to embody TS communal strength. As regards etymology, I think that especially makers of Romanian dictionaries should thoroughly study early Transylvanian attestations, for a very simple reason: as mentioned above, the earliest texts in Romanian were written and/or printed as late as the 16th century, whereas village names based on Romanian common words were recorded much earlier in Transylvanian documents written in Medieval Latin, German or Hungarian. For a spectacular example, whereas the noun *cornăţel* (cf. MDA-I, s.v. *cornăţel*¹) was first recorded in a botanical book published in 1929, the village name *Cornachel* (today's *Cornăţel*) was recorded more than six centuries before, in 1306 (see above). These and other facts²⁷ should encourage other researchers to approach – from as many angles as possible – early records of Transylvanian geographic names.

²⁵ In that case, the main records given by Suciu (1968: 251) are the following: 1231 *villa Albe ecclesie*; 1297 *Feyereghaz* (cf. H *fëhér* 'white' + *egyház* 'church'); 1494 *Vyskirch*; 1760 *Weisskirch*; 1854 *Szász Fejéregyháza*, *Weisskirch*, *Giscriu* (the last one reflecting a dialectal Romanian pronunciation of *Viscri*).

²⁶ See <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-europe-53984239> (6 September 2020).

²⁷ Even specialists concerned with the history of Roma communities in Transylvania could find interesting clues in Suciu's dictionary (volume 2), which contains entries such as the one on *Czyganfalwa* (Cluj) – as name of a village recorded in 1505, but vanished in the meantime – or the one on *Țigăneştii de Criş* (Bihor), as name of a still extant village, which was first recorded in 1507, as *Czyganfalwa* (cf. H *cigány* 'gypsy' + *falu* 'village').

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